

Evidence Basis Transdermal Medicinal Kit Therapy used in Management of Low Back Pain: A Review Study of AyurvedaGyan Prakash¹, Anurag Pandey², Mamta Tiwari³¹Clinical Research Director, Bahamani Geriatric Rehabilitation Centre and Ayurveda Hospital Bandhtoli-Shukurhuttu, Post- Hulhundu, Dist.-Ranchi - 835221, Jharkhand, India²Research Advisor, Bahamani Geriatric Rehabilitation Centre and Ayurveda Hospital Bandhtoli-Shukurhuttu, Post- Hulhundu, Dist.-Ranchi - 835221, Jharkhand, India³Research Advisor, Bahamani Geriatric Rehabilitation Centre and Ayurveda Hospital Bandhtoli-Shukurhuttu, Post- Hulhundu, Dist.-Ranchi - 835221, Jharkhand, India

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Abstract:

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in terms of such damage. Ref.: international Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) where other such as emotional distress or spiritual distress may induce the same overall feeling as a physical injury. In textual reference of Ayurveda, the symptom pain is closely related to Shula or Vedna. In this condition, the vitiated humor Vata is localized in different regions of body like Asthi, Sandhi, Kati, and Prushtha and produces pain. When Vata gets vitiated, it dries up the ligament of the joints and constricts the Snayu present there and causes pain at that joint. Snehan swedan are Ayurvedic therapies, Snehan (Abhyanga) means oleation therapy which produces Snigdghata or oiliness in the body. It involves massaging the entire body or parts of body with a specific Doshahar warm herb-infused oil. Swedan is usually performed after Snehan. Swedan is an inert body heat therapy by which sweat or perspiration is produced in the body, making individual feel lighter, smoother and more energized. In recent era Transdermal Medicinal Kit Therapy (TDMKT) has got prominent place in the management of the disease through Ayurveda, Because TDMKT is only hope in patients who are bushed after all the Shamana treatments. TDMKT expels the Doshas form their causative roots so disease cannot revert after; like tree cannot grow without its root. Without proper Poorvakarma physician cannot get truly result though Shodhana procedure (like Vamana/Virechana) performed well, because without Poorvakarmas Doshas cannot be changed in particular forms through which they can be expelled out form the body. The present paper is focused on explanation of the principle that how Poorvakarma is essential for Shodhana therapy, how they change Doshas' form and elucidate the kala and Matra of Poorvakarma particular in Snehapana.

Keywords: Transdermal Medicinal Kit Therapy (TDMKT), Pain, (vata-viyadhi), Snehan (Abhyanga), Swedan Karma, Receptor pathways.

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Introduction

In recent era TDMKT has got prominent place in the management of the diseases through Ayurveda, as it is widely practiced by most of the Ayurvedic physicians but sometime, we observe that through the same TDMKT procedures a physician gets marvelous result while sometime he may not. So many causes may be there for that, but while going through the Shodhana therapy; physician should perform Poorvakarmas as primacy.

Without Poorvakarmas Doshas cannot be changed in particular forms through which they can be expelled out from the body. [1] Shodhana would be easy to perform if Poorvakarmas were done properly. [2] Same approach is applied in the modern surgery; patients who are physically and

psychologically well prepared for surgery tend to have better surgical outcomes. Preoperative care is extremely important prior to any invasive procedure whether the procedure is minimally invasive or a form of major surgery. [3] In this study we have tried to explain the importance of Poorvakarmas in a Shodhana therapy.

TDMKT is helpful for those patients who are bushed after all the Shamana treatments because TDMKT expels the Doshas from their causative roots, so diseases cannot revert after; like tree cannot grow without its root. [4] TDMKT can be performed whenever Doshas are available in Koshthas (Upasthita Doshani) in particular form of the suitable person. [5] Here commentator

Chakrapani has explained that Doshas which are accumulating from Shakhas to Koshtas from all over the body and Doshas which have changed their forms from Linatva to Utkleshita can be said as Upasthitadoshas. [6] Five causes are responsible for the movement of Doshas from Shakhas to Koshtas like; 1) Vriddhi of the Doshas 2) Vishyandana of the Doshas 3) Paka of Doshas 4) Srotomukha Vishodhana 5) Nigrahana of Vata. [7] These all five causes can be achieved by the Poorvakarmas i.e. Snehana and Swedana. Internal Snehapana plays a key role in Vriddhi of the Doshas. Sneha does Dosha Vriddhi (Shodhanartha Sneha), Doshashamana or Brihanakarma, if it uses in particular Matra (quantity) and Kala (time). [8]

1) **Vriddhi of the Doshas:** For Vriddhi of the Doshas, Sneha is consumed in empty stomach in the morning (after digestion of previous night meal) in such a dose which takes about 12 or 24 hours to digest. For Dosha Shamana, after digestion of the previous night meal when the patient feels hungry at that time Sneha is consumed in such a dose which takes about 12 hours to digest and for

Brihanakarma, Sneha is consumed along with the food, in such a dose which takes about 6 hours to digest. [9]

2) **Vishyandana of the Doshas:** Definition of Snehana itself says that Sneha does Vishyandanakarma. [10]

3) **Paka of Doshas:** Here Swedana Karma plays a key role because Ushnata is essential Guna in the Swedana Karma and Ushna Guna does Pachanakarma. [11]

4) **Srotomukhavishodhana (to clean the orifices of Srotas):** While describing the benefits of the Swedana Karma, Acharya Sushruta says that Swedana creates Nirmalatva (cleanliness) in the Srotas. [12] So Swedana cleans the orifices of Srotas.

5) **Nigrahana of Vata:** The first line of management of Vatadosha according to Acharya Vagbhatta is Snehana and Swedana. [13] So Vatadosha can be controlled (Nigrahana) very well by the Snehana and Swedana.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Result

After the research basis therapy and management of Low Back Pain by ayurveda medical science found 95% excellent therapy for those having not any pathological issues and regular taking any pain killer from chemist.

03% found negative result those uses in daily life information technology devices during his school and work and GIT disorder, stress, depression, anxiety, alcohol, tobacco and toxic food from street food supply hawker.

02% found not any result those patients are use to addict for the narcotise, drugs abuse, late night sleep habit, long driving in AC car and sever psychological disorders.

Figure 3:

Research Data of Low Back Pain Patients with Category Age 31-40 Group B

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Result

After the research basis therapy and management of Low Back Pain by ayurveda medical science found 90% excellent therapy for those patients having not any pathological issues and not taking regular any pain killer from chemist.

06% found negative result those patients uses in daily life information technology devices during his school and work and GIT disorder, stress, depression, anxiety, alcohol, tobacco and toxic food from street food supply hawker. The female patient are untreated and taking long period of medicine in diseases of uncontrol menstruation period, PCOD, diabetes, THS, HTN and life style, late night sleep, constipation, alcoholic, HIV, typhoid, malaria.

04% found not any result those patients arc use to addict for the narcotise, drugs abuse, late night sleep habit, long driving in AC car and sever psychological disorders.

Figure 6:

Research Data of Low Back Pain Patients with Category Age 41-80 Group C

Figure 7:

Figure 8:

Result

After the research basis therapy and management of Low Back Pain by ayurveda medical science found 90% excellent therapy for those having not any pathological issues and regular taking any pain killer from chemist.

07% found negative result those uses in daily life information technology devices during his school and work and GIT disorder, stress, depression, anxiety, alcohol, tobacco and toxic food from street food supply hawker. The female patient are untreated and taking long period of medicine in diseases of uncontrol menstruation period, PCOD, diabetes, THS, HTN and life style, late night sleep, constipation, alcoholic, HIV, typhoid, malaria, taking poly medicament oral and injectable.

03% found not any result those patients are use to addict for the narcotise, drugs abuse, late night sleep habit, long driving in AC car and sever psychological disorders.

Figure 9:

Discussion

Shodhana Karma means elimination of Doshas from the body. [14] For that physician has to, bring Doshas from Shakha to Koshta and change the form of Doshas through which they can be easily removed from the body.[15] These can be done only by Snehana and Swedana Karmas. Five causes are responsible for the movement of Doshas from Shakhas to the Koshtas like Vriddhi of the Doshas, Vishyandana of the Doshas, Paka of Doshas, Srotomukha Vishodhana and Nigrahana of Vata. [16] Vriddhi of doshas can be done after the Nidana Sevana, but Nidana Sevana may not be able to change the form of the Doshas to Vishyandana simultaneously. Vriddhi of Doshas can be achieved only if Snehapana is done on particular Kala, i.e. an empty stomach in the morning when previous night meal gets digested. [17]

Three types of Karmas (functions) have been mentioned which can be achieved by Snehana if it is used according to Matra and Kala. They are Dosh Vriddhi (Shodhanartha Snehana), Dosh Shamana (Shamanartha Snehana) and Brimhana. [18] Samskarasyaanuvartana property of Snehana, [19], especially in Ghrita is responsible for all three types of Karmas. Samskara means putting together. [20] So Snehana is given in empty stomach in afternoon when the person feels hungry, it combines (have samskara) with Agni not with Doshas because Agni digests Doshas if Anna (food) is not present, [21] so consumed Snehana causes Agnidipti further it does Doshapachana in extent level. Now considering the Kala of Shodhanartha Snehapana, an empty stomach in the morning; at that time the state of Agni is not capable to perform Doshapachana, so consumed Snehana will be combined (have samskara) with

Doshas and causes for Vriddhi of Doshas. [22] Same principle is applied for Brihana Snehapana, if Snehana combines with Anna it surges the nutritional quality of Anna and creates Brihanakarma.

Matra of Snehana also has much important as Kala. If it is taken on Shodhanarthakala in such a dose which takes about 12 hours to digest, it is ideal Snehapana for Shodhanakarma. [23] The dose of Snehana should be increased in gradual manner as Acharya Charaka has mentioned minimum 3 and maximum 7 days to achieve all the characteristics of proper Snehana according to Koshta. [24] Hence one should not complete Snehapana in one day. Second cause for gradual increasing the dose of Snehana during Snehapana is to acquire maximum utility of Snehana as Acharya Charaka says, if Snehapana is not done gradually, it flushes out entirely from the body (without affecting body) like water poured over an earthen mass quickly flows out without moistening it. [25]

Definition of Snehana itself says that, it creates Vishyandata. [26] Vishyanditata means Vilayana (dissolve). Lina Doshas are difficult to eliminate in their own forms, Snehana creates the suitable forms of Doshas for elimination. Snehana also facilitate passage of Utkleshita Doshas in Srotas and Doshas float without adhesion in the body, like honey kept in a pot smeared with fat, toward the Koshta. [27]

Ushana Guna is indispensable quality for the Swedana [28] because in Swedana there is always Agnisamskara either directly or indirectly. [29] So Doshas get digested by the Pachana property of the Ushnaswedana. Here Tikshnaguna of Swedana also helps in Pachana. [30]

Swedana not only digests Doshas (Paka by the Agnidipti) but it cleans the orifices of Srotas

(also Srotomukha) consecutively. So without Swedana Karma movement of Doshas cannot be achieved. Vriddhi of the Doshas, Vishyandana of the Doshas, Paka of Doshas, Srotomukhavishodhana, these all functions are conducted only by Snehana and Swedana altogether, which was discussed previously. With these, physician does not need extra efforts for Nigrahana of Vata, because Snehana and Swedana are the foremost treatment for Vata. In addition to this, form of Doshas transformed to Klinnatva and Dravatva by Snehana and Swedana respectively, [31] which is necessary for the movement of Doshas toward the Koshta as well as for elimination from the body. Snigdha guna is indispensable quality for the Snehana [32] and Snigdha guna does the Kledanakarma. [33] Dravaguna of Snehana also helps in Kledanakarma. [34] Ushna and Tikshnagunas of the Swedana transform Doshas in Drava form. [35]

Transdermal Medicinal Kit Therapy (TDMKT) (Snehana and Swedana)

Transdermal medicinal kit therapy Snehana and Swedana are used evidence basis practice of low back pain. Snehana or Medicinal Oleation therapy helps in loosening the body toxins which are stuck up into our body systems causing ailments. Oleation is of two type's internal and external oleation, where in internal oleation Snehana dravya like plain or medicated ghee, oil is taken orally in desirable amount. External Oleation therapy consists of whole or partial body massage with medicated oils. Our skin being semi-permeable absorbs this oil to some extent, under receptor pathways in the body.

Swedan or Sudation therapy is sweating induced by medicated kit with 14 types of ayurvedic ingredient, it liquifies the toxins and increases the flow of toxins to anatomical organs system there is main Gastrointestinal track (Koshtha). There are various ways of applying swedan therapy like Nadi sweda, Pinda sweda, Patra Pottali, Valuka sweda, etc. the type of sweda to be used is selected according to the patient and the disease he is suffering from. Similarly, there are other associated procedures apart from these basis five therapies which will be dealt further but to mention a few they are: Shirodhara, Shirobasti, Karnapurana, Pizicchil, Tailadahara, Nabhipura, Hrid Basti, Manya Basti, etc.

One challenging aspect of measuring such a cleansing program is that theoretically, subjects may feel worse on the way to feeling better. Ayurveda address this as the body's cleansing mechanism and other TDMKT label such reaction as "healing crises". Given this, the researchers were surprised that there were no serious side effects reported and a low level or reported mild side

effects, such as gastrointestinal upset or brief insomnia. At baseline, 23% of subjects reported mild side effects, such as most likely represent the effects of the pre-program dietary changes and the experience of everyday life. the moderate level of reported side effects rose insignificantly to 26% after 6 days at the retreat. While this result is positive, we were disappointed that our main hypothesis was not supported; there were also no significant changes, positive or negative, in general symptoms as measured by the SF-12 [43]. There are many possible explanations for this: a true lack of benefit to overall quality of life, the negative effects of the cleansing process were balanced by any positive effects, or the self-report measurement was not sensitive in this sample. We were also surprised that anxiety decreased significantly at 3 months' post treatment, but not immediately after treatment; this could be an indication of the situational anxiety caused by the deep cleansing program, and lack or ability to rely on home-based behavior patterns and comfortable routines.

While we did not find evidence that overall quality of life was improved through the use of TDMKT, as a program of behavior change, our preliminary results suggest that the complex intervention may be effective in assisting one's actual and expected adherence to new and healthier behavior patterns. That is, with statistical significance, following the intervention, the Lifestyle Profile II showed a greater frequency of positive patterns and subjects reported greater self-efficacy in using Ayurveda to promote health changes.

It also appears that the perceived social support might be part of the mechanism of these changes. With a larger sample and adequate controls, we could model social support as a mediator or modifier of behavior change. Yet it may be more appropriate to consider the social world as a necessary part of a holistic intervention. While social factors may mediate one's ability to achieve a certain outcome, considering such changes exclusively in a linear manner, at least in the beginning of an investigation, would impede our ability to see how factors are related to each other. Research in this area has indicated that the addition of social support, even as a piece of a larger intervention, may not be effective [42]. Perhaps an important mechanism in complex TDMKT systems is the very thing that subjects report enjoying most-the patient is considered as a whole, in context [41]. Social support is not an added factor, but an emergent quality of the system. This is supported by other research that shows that behavior change programs are more effective the more relevant the messages are or how well the program is incorporated into the person's regular life [37]. Behavior change programs work better when the program is made salient to the subject.

Improving perceived social support might be a way to improve salience and social support may be easily influenced through holistic systems. If this is true, then it points to new questions in the area of health behavior research. One frustration to health behavior scientists is that, generally, important aspects of subjects's social world are nonmodifiable. Many of our health risks are affected by our social determinants - race, gender, education - factors that are not modifiable in the context of complex TDMKT medical interventions for the very reason that such interventions work inherently on the level of the subject's social world.

But how do we know that we modified perceived social support and did not just add new social connections? While not a main study outcome, we wanted to consider this question and thus we also measured the subjects' reported social network index [36] at the same three data collection points. The social network index is a structural measure of the subject's social contacts and the use of those contacts. No significant reported changes were found following Panchakarma in this structural measure. This is interesting because it supports the idea that perceived social support could be increased without actual structural changes in the social network. The way that the subject thinks about his/her social world changes, even if no new individuals are added; it is a perceptual and phenomenological change, not a structural change. Adding supportive people may help, but this study suggests that changing the individual's perceptions, without adding people, may also be important.

Much research has shown that perceptual factors, such as quality of life and expectation about health, are predictive of overall health [37,38]. Holistic health interventions may offer insights on how to modify lived experience. In such a holistic world view, lived or phenomenological experiences are factors or symptoms that can be treated. This project also included the collection of three qualitative interviews conducted prior to the retreat, immediately after, and 3 months' post retreat. The interviews investigated the subject's health history, health practices, expectations of treatment, and experiences with the Panchakarma program. A future step for this project is to analyse the qualitative interview data in order to add a phenomenological understanding of this process, and perhaps to link phenomenology with standardized outcomes. If the qualities of lived experience are related to later disease outcomes, then examining and modifying such qualities may be helpful in disease prevention. This idea is utilized in other well-studied health sciences [39,40], so learning more about how Ayurveda models such relationships will likely add to our scientific understanding of the mechanisms of health and healing.

Evidence basis therapy are used in the management of low back pain of 12 months with the age group 14-30 Group A (total 20 patients), 31-40 Group B (total 38 patients), and age 41-80 Group C (total 125 patients) Total patients was $A+B+C=183$ The research attempt to explore the concept of pain in classical texts of Ayurveda in light of modern science. Re-exploring of therapeutic pain management strategies which are validated & effective treatment in Ayurveda of Sneha, Swedan Transdermal Medicinal Kit Therapy (TDMKT). The management of pain itself is still under research persistently as it is subjective parameter with different threshold for different individuals. Current research is an attempt to cover the maximum aspects of pain treatment & throw an emphasis on probable mode of action of the chief therapeutic procedures utilized in pain treatment in Ayurveda but as the symptom being subjective: it depends on the patient, site, extent and stage of the disease and hence doesn't offer the most appropriate modality for pain relief.

Main aim of the treatment is to pacify vitiated Vata Dosha, TDMKT pain management are safe and natural ways that help in the management of different kinds of pain. Increase in the pain threshold and reduction of the cause of pain is a whole new approach towards pain. To conclude, it is a Herculean task to cover entire concept of pain management in Ayurveda. There are treatment modalities in TDMKT which need validation leaving a scope for future research in pain management through Ayurveda. [44,45,46]

Conclusion

This research is an attempt to explore the concept of Pain in classical texts of Ayurveda in light of modern science. Re-exploring of therapeutic pain management strategies which are validated & effective treatment in Ayurveda of Sneha, Swedan are discussed to help one to understand the modulation of pain in light of modern concepts. Many other facets of vitiation Vata Dosha & Pain as for example treatment of Vatavyadhi (disorders due to vitiated Vata Dosha) chiefly are us of purview of this article. The management of Pain itself is still under research persistently as it is a subjective parameter with different threshold for different individuals. Current research is an attempt to cover the maximum aspects of pain treatment & throw an emphasis on probable mode of action of the chief therapeutic procedures utilized in pain treatment in Ayurveda but as the symptom being subjective: it depends on the patient, site, extent and stage of the disease and hence doesn't offer the most appropriate modality for pain relief. Main aim of the treatment is to pacify vitiated Vata Dosha. Ayurvedic pain management of safe and natural ways that helps in the management of different kinds of pain, increase in the pain threshold and

reduction of the cause of pain is a whole new approach towards pain. There are treatment modalities in Ayurveda which needs therapeutic validation leaving a scope for future research in pain management through Ayurveda. Panchakarma can be performed only if the Doshas are available in the Koshta from all over the body. For that Snehana and Swedana Karmas are the merely options. Five causes responsible for the movement of Doshas from the Shakha to Koshta, Vriddhi and Vishayandana of the Dosha can be done prudishly by Snehanakarma while Swedana does Srotomukha Vishodhana and Paka of Doshas. Physician can control (Nigrahana) Vatadosha certainly by Snehana and Swedana Karmas. Snehanakarma can cause for Vriddhi of Doshas only, if it is consumed in empty stomach at that time when agni is not in increased state, otherwise it increases Agni not Dosh.

Sneha especially Ghrita is imperative factor in treatment due to its Samskarasya Anuvartana quality. With this Guna it causes for Vriddhi, Shamana of Doshas or Brimhana of the body. Practically the dose of Sneha for Shodhanakarma should be that, which takes about 12 hours to get digested. Snehanakarma is an imperious Poorvakarma. In a nut shell without performing Poorvakarmas, Doshas cannot accumulate into the Koshta in a particular form for the Shodhana.

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